

Circle packing inside a regular tetradecagon: supplemental material

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Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 200$ congruent disks packed inside a regular tetradecagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular tetradecagon that we have found using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 200$. Although we cannot claim that these configurations correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, they provide good lower bounds to the packing fraction. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader should refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular tetradecagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 200$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 200$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceed by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is large:

configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular tetradecagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.493652404307	0.504139779747	41	0.135470519964	0.778308745921
3	0.454819312439	0.641914975875	42	0.134005919665	0.780145694635
4	0.406873105274	0.684946130984	43	0.132508412915	0.780969042458
5	0.362829076901	0.680851863726	44	0.131173841559	0.78311512141
6	0.3288226783	0.671047455149	45	0.129981471472	0.786418770061
7	0.325805629975	0.768588121138	46	0.128779750527	0.789098920177
8	0.300256863661	0.746026635144	47	0.127551079457	0.790941918893
9	0.271660289557	0.687026179638	48	0.126176578488	0.790455069228
10	0.25800068328	0.688525724358	49	0.124821404791	0.789682785009
11	0.25012618399	0.711851588501	50	0.124272326913	0.798725083483
12	0.244457938075	0.741767828043	51	0.122459007395	0.791097668189
13	0.23182361968	0.722665257044	52	0.121502456944	0.794057445441
14	0.22733253392	0.748392936175	53	0.120519968944	0.796291995828
15	0.217889144008	0.736615584665	54	0.119723437859	0.800627635277
16	0.212612663912	0.7481293606	55	0.11912681695	0.807346976766
17	0.205930729626	0.745709535239	56	0.117590951198	0.800966389367
18	0.201644753853	0.757050444385	57	0.116519262571	0.800476836101
19	0.201215647902	0.795711367238	58	0.115609504706	0.801850738015
20	0.192142389595	0.763756341555	59	0.114525607078	0.800452702613
21	0.187414903167	0.762967430104	60	0.113541408015	0.800088927159
22	0.182427174352	0.757321352757	61	0.112922695688	0.804582843501
23	0.17916635368	0.763693694687	62	0.111726413141	0.800537832251
24	0.17560128263	0.765499775659	63	0.110912603469	0.801642635803
25	0.171564066784	0.761151542371	64	0.110014176004	0.801227290029
26	0.169066629971	0.768718969658	65	0.109285860279	0.803007803641
27	0.166464003051	0.773896515007	66	0.108607129867	0.805265453226
28	0.163544012412	0.774650467026	67	0.107691064334	0.803734479622
29	0.160421750958	0.771974510669	68	0.106805193979	0.802365261274
30	0.158737022368	0.781908928146	69	0.106005847783	0.802023690019
31	0.155361076522	0.773970835571	70	0.105330756403	0.803316901489
32	0.153063596127	0.775482964752	71	0.10463779593	0.804107242197
33	0.151326333506	0.781666352377	72	0.104123251922	0.80743282596
34	0.1488096437	0.778788498876	73	0.103331383311	0.806242718571
35	0.146878354364	0.781019898706	74	0.102888559691	0.810297228827
36	0.145528481503	0.78863664792	75	0.102017099608	0.807394276216
37	0.144752841409	0.801926153338	76	0.101532384366	0.81040333799
38	0.141312337297	0.784914251349	77	0.100642952831	0.806744334877
39	0.139542815184	0.785521409365	78	0.100043680469	0.80751831674
40	0.138029977789	0.78828867275	79	0.0993668877304	0.806842794345

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular tetradecagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.0989751653429	0.810626724597	121	0.0808383993311	0.817898176429
81	0.0986102890699	0.8147191813	122	0.080455571676	0.816865472025
82	0.0979384461982	0.813577126737	123	0.0801182740454	0.816670258532
83	0.0975235056062	0.816535665794	124	0.0797860271012	0.816495553579
84	0.0967405498666	0.813157829007	125	0.0794962435471	0.817112183737
85	0.0962781761932	0.814991527338	126	0.0791571920184	0.816638335875
86	0.0955040969039	0.811373677351	127	0.0788988265663	0.81775511217
87	0.0948315775231	0.809289044592	128	0.0787125590274	0.820307140874
88	0.0942705645868	0.808934479379	129	0.0782992494385	0.818056626397
89	0.0937461968158	0.809050780041	130	0.0780828648161	0.819847900352
90	0.0931516121911	0.807796039157	131	0.0777243380595	0.818585067949
91	0.0926367575262	0.807767809017	132	0.0775032324792	0.820147607482
92	0.0921607113287	0.808272721761	133	0.0772445243357	0.820853219411
93	0.0916681642463	0.808348199887	134	0.077031026609	0.822459702965
94	0.0912987015028	0.810467331239	135	0.0767863147233	0.823341253359
95	0.0908015939818	0.810193973972	136	0.0765106855557	0.823496113095
96	0.0904595461599	0.812565727479	137	0.0763805156635	0.826730952637
97	0.0900234633441	0.813133074685	138	0.0759927995428	0.824332519703
98	0.0895810925199	0.81346195046	139	0.0756011573968	0.821769744
99	0.0891648409985	0.814143447806	140	0.0753964666473	0.823205913755
100	0.0888576740457	0.816710878326	141	0.0752166415711	0.825135833211
101	0.0883010003105	0.814575004061	142	0.0750422980118	0.827140055612
102	0.0877725957662	0.812823993294	143	0.0748855655485	0.829489177345
103	0.0874256513751	0.814316878777	144	0.0743807913652	0.824067032096
104	0.0870584672754	0.815330767919	145	0.0740789526983	0.823068779448
105	0.0865647531104	0.813860455296	146	0.0737499593049	0.821400351417
106	0.0862503312386	0.81565380602	147	0.0735539601841	0.822636384265
107	0.0857789714695	0.814374010334	148	0.0733505761623	0.82365859173
108	0.0853950203525	0.814642956227	149	0.0731303917976	0.824252982494
109	0.0850137361688	0.814860305183	150	0.0729589461859	0.825898775978
110	0.0845809971411	0.813985643761	151	0.0727587718102	0.826848846134
111	0.0842479107978	0.814928895506	152	0.0725726707931	0.828072302848
112	0.0839789854645	0.817029482989	153	0.0723875743944	0.829273787308
113	0.0836520305739	0.817918209382	154	0.0721300146485	0.828764653186
114	0.0833711467178	0.819624364289	155	0.0718821104667	0.828422328257
115	0.083056484743	0.820584654897	156	0.0716505521601	0.828403909824
116	0.0827720355939	0.822060383703	157	0.0714237117165	0.828443590555
117	0.0823904687909	0.821520240812	158	0.0711756974491	0.827940273398
118	0.0819740725315	0.820188147833	159	0.0709652900792	0.828261639147
119	0.0816510617778	0.820633219049	160	0.0706657777719	0.826450273654
120	0.0812524041539	0.819468274584	161	0.0705298216346	0.828418722744

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular tetradecagon for $162 \leq N \leq 200$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.0702420030389	0.826774832758	182	0.0665093285665	0.832750636921
163	0.0699772579448	0.825619428575	183	0.0663832106592	0.83415365135
164	0.0698103645963	0.826726995245	184	0.0661731772789	0.833412973621
165	0.0696925344794	0.828962567313	185	0.0660472012996	0.834754993734
166	0.0695160386517	0.829767801965	186	0.0657953881476	0.832879761971
167	0.069395852776	0.831882452783	187	0.0655995440613	0.832380134523
168	0.0692689642761	0.833806215696	188	0.0653819154766	0.831288145755
169	0.069073709535	0.834047381272	189	0.0652650082264	0.832723952453
170	0.0688017619068	0.832389321019	190	0.0650427091556	0.831436916851
171	0.0685785050004	0.831860677765	191	0.064926574998	0.832830867064
172	0.0682642161041	0.829073665192	192	0.0647615996247	0.832942116255
173	0.0681060013819	0.830032939278	193	0.064606619355	0.833277778673
174	0.0679038555238	0.829882438737	194	0.0645450414515	0.835999382294
175	0.0677272108307	0.830315009299	195	0.0643310788844	0.834746755573
176	0.0675442780188	0.830554726543	196	0.0641916969016	0.83539571368
177	0.067374221656	0.8310731412	197	0.0639813217178	0.834163340203
178	0.0672533531535	0.832772443356	198	0.063814365741	0.834027869286
179	0.0670684447601	0.832852245187	199	0.0636758265433	0.834604490361
180	0.0668283949231	0.831520622206	200	0.0635143212564	0.834548876744
181	0.066646496806	0.831594648228			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tetradecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

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References

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